

SOME FEATURES OF THE TERMINOLOGICAL TRAINING OF UZBEK-SPEAKING STUDENTS OF MEDICAL PEDIATRIC UNIVERSITY

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Annotation: *The article is devoted to the methodological problems of mastering the Latin language by national students.*

Key words: *Latin language, teaching methods at the university, national students.*

Аннотация: *Статья посвящена методическим проблемам освоения латинского языка национальными студентами.*

Ключевые слова: *латинский язык, методика преподавания в вузе, национальные студенты.*

Annotatsiya: *Maqola milliy talabalarni atamashunoslikka tayyorlashning uslubiy muammolariga bag'ishlangan.*

Tayanch soʻzlar: *Tibbiyot terminologiyasi, fanni oʻqitish metodikasi, milliy talabalar, muammolar va ularning yechimlari.*

The formation of communicative competence among foreign students is one of the most important and complex methodological components of the learning process at a medical university. When working with Uzbek students, the teacher should take into account the native language of students, the level of their basic pre-university training, the motivation for choosing a profession and the desire to master the chosen specialty.

For the purpose of teaching and communicating with Uzbek students, as a rule, English or Russian is currently used, which has the status of the language of international communication. This approach contributes to the solution of a whole range of methodological problems: the effective implementation of the teacher's professional mission, an accurate understanding of the value orientations and attitudes of students at an early stage of their education at the university, taking into account the needs of students for self-realization.

In recent years, the program of teaching Uzbek students in English has firmly entered the practice of medical and pharmaceutical universities. Knowledge of English allows leveling the problems associated with ethnic and national diversity in the student group. More than 30 years of experience in teaching under the English Medium program at our university shows that due to the use of English in the educational process at the stage of initial training of future doctors, the time for their sociocultural and professional adaptation is significantly reduced.

The teachers of our department have significant experience in working with Uzbek students studying in Russian and English. In particular, at present, classes are being held in groups of national students in the compulsory academic discipline "Latin".

The study of Latin is of fundamental importance for the general cultural development of students, as well as for their successful development of the medical profession.

Teaching Latin stimulates logical thinking, broadens the general outlook of students, aims them at the effective study of basic subjects. In medical schools in Latin classes, students study the phonetic structure of the Latin language and the basics of Latin grammar, as well as cycles of anatomical, clinical and pharmaceutical terminology. In parallel with the Latin language, first-year students study anatomy, where a good knowledge of the Latin language, its vocabulary and grammar, is necessary.

For the majority of national students currently studying at our institute, English is becoming one of the main means of communication along with their

native languages. It is a high level of English language proficiency that is a factor that teachers purposefully use to optimize the educational process and master a lot of factual material. In most cases, our students easily learn medical vocabulary in Latin, since it was the Latin language that had a significant influence on the formation of the English language. But in the process of studying the discipline "Latin", various problems arise associated with a real violation of the system and norms of the Latin language under the influence of English. The main task of the teacher is to develop methodological techniques that help mitigate the interfering influence of the English language.

Already at the first lessons in Latin (studying the alphabet, phonetic and orthoepic norms), students have an erroneous idea that they are familiar with the material being studied, and no additional efforts will be required to master it. The teacher has to draw students' attention to the difference in the names of some letters in the Latin and English alphabets, to a significant difference in the pronunciation of sounds and words, and also to devote more time to developing literate reading skills in Latin. When getting acquainted with new lexical material (common, special and terminological vocabulary), it is important to draw students' attention to the pronunciation features of single-root words, since it is in the pronunciation of such verbal units that the greatest interfering influence of the English language is manifested.

In addition, students often have grammatical errors associated with the difference in the system of Latin and English - English is an analytical language (grammatical relations in it are transmitted through separate functional words), and Latin is recognized as a synthetic language (grammatical relations in it are expressed within words).

Thus, in Latin, the relation of a noun to another word is conveyed by means of a case ending, and in English, by a noun in combination with a certain preposition.

Also in English, unlike Latin, gender cannot be determined by a formal indicator - it is identified by the lexical meaning of the word or by the contextual

environment. Thus, our student is faced with the task of accurately determining the gender of a noun, which is necessary for the correct declension of the noun and its agreement with the adjective.

Greek-Latin terminology is traditionally the "thesaurus" (in the broad sense of the word) of international medical science, i.e. includes all the basic concepts and terms of medicine, without the knowledge of which meaningful assimilation of its constituent special subjects and disciplines is impossible. The experience of teaching Latin in groups of national students shows that when studying the lexical composition of anatomical, clinical and pharmaceutical terminology, students do not experience serious difficulties, since the English language contains a large number of borrowings from Latin.

Medical terms in English often have a common root with Latin terms, they largely coincide in their sound and graphic design. Difficulties in the process of teaching students arise when mastering the word-formation system of the Latin language. Therefore, when studying the word-building elements of the Latin language, one should pay attention to the most regular prefixes and suffixes of Greek-Latin origin.

An important aspect in the study of the lexical composition of the Latin language is associative links. In groups studying under the "English Medium" program, in the absence of exact synonyms in the language, associative series are built by using a variety of visual material. In groups studying in Russian, all the efforts of students are aimed at memorizing terminological correspondences: "Latin word" - "Russian word". In the field of teaching lexical material at further stages, foreign students freely memorize lexical units not only by the formal indicators of words in the English language, but also by associative links, identifying the new with the already known in the Russian language.

The key indicator in the development of honed skills and abilities in the process of mastering Latin medical terminology is the active use of practical exercises and test tasks.

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